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Strength and Failure Modes in Resistance Welded Thermoplastic Composite Joints: Effect of Fiber-Matrix Adhesion

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Outline

1

Introduction of Resistance Welding

2

Experiment and Results

3

Team Work

1. Introduction of Resistance Welding

Joining technology of thermoplastic composites is a key step to **improve the production efficiency**. The study of different joining processes has been favored by more and more experts and scholars.

1. Introduction of Resistance Welding

The thermoplastic composite welding technology is mainly divided into four types: electromagnetic welding, friction welding, thermal welding and electrical welding.

Resistance Welding

Joule's law

$$P = \frac{I^2 R}{l \times w} \quad \left[\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2} \right]$$

$$E = P \times t \quad \left[\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{m}^2} \right]$$

Induction Welding

Fusion Bonding Techniques

Microwave Welding

Laser Welding

Hot Tool Welding

Ultrasonic Welding

1. Introduction of Resistance Welding

Comprehensive comparison of three joining technologies

Comprehensive comparison of three Welding technologies

Evaluation of Complexity, Efficiency and Component Size

Technological parameter

the important parameter factors of this technology includes welding time, pressure, current, heat element size and so on. In this speech, we develop some study on the influence of heat element size

2. Experiment and Results

4 Kinds of heat elements

Size	100	200	300	400
a/ μm	75	50	40	30
b/ μm	385	180	125	100

Preparation Process

the tensile strength and modulus of these samples are test according to ASTM D882

Tensile Strength and modulus of PEEK heat elements

2. Experiment and Results

Temperature Control

Temperature curves for different kinds of PEEK heat elements with different currents

100

200

300

400

As the process temperature of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composites is 350~450 degrees Celsius, the currents were choose for different kinds of samples, respectively.

2. Experiment and Results

Specimen Preparation — ASTM D1002

Tensile Examination

Tensile Strength

All the specimens were cut into the proper size according to ASTM D1002, and the tensile examination carried out in mechanical testing machine.

2. Experiment and Results

Metallographs of intersecting surface

100

200

300

400

Fracture Surface

100

200

300

400

the failure modes of all the samples is apparently different, including interlaminar failure mode, interfacial failure mode and cohesive failure mode

2. Experiment and Results

SEM photographs of the Fracture Surface

100

50x

50x

200

50x

50x

200x

200x

200x

200x

2. Experiment and Results

SEM photographs of the Fracture Surface

300

50x

50x

400

50x

50x

200x

200x

200x

200x

2. Experiment and Results

100

400

Digimat

3. Team Work

Enhanced interfacial interactions of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composites by regulating PEI and graphene oxide complex sizing at the interface

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Fig. The scheme of preparation of PEI/GO modified carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composites.

COMPOSITES SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Fig. SEM and AFM images of carbon fiber surfaces after sizing.

Fig. Interfacial shear strength.

Fig. Interlaminar shear strength.

Fig. Flexural strength.

Fig. Schematic illustration of bonding mechanism.

3. Team Work

Multiscale Enhancement Behavior of Nano-Silica Modified CF/PEEK Composites Prepared by Wet Powder Impregnation

Polymer composites

Fig. The scheme of preparation of nano-silica modified CF/PEEK composites.

Fig. ILSS failure images near the fiber surfaces.

Fig. Interlaminar shear strength

Fig. Flexural properties.

Fig. Illustration of damage development.

3. Team Work

Effect of Preheat Treatment on Carbon Fiber Surface Properties and Fiber/PEEK Interfacial Behavior

Polymer composites

Microbond test

Fig. The scheme of preparation of CF/PEEK microbond test samples.

Fig. Surface morphologies of CFs after preheat treatment at different temperatures.

Fig. Infrared spectrum of CFs after preheat treatment at different temperatures

Fig. Change of IFSS and activated carbon atoms content on CF surface.

Fig. Surface morphologies of debonded fibers in microbond test.

Thank You for Your Attention !

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